

POWER MAPS IN FINITE GROUPS

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Abstract

In recent work, Pomerance and Shparlinski have obtained results on the number of cycles in the functional graph of the map $x \mapsto x^a$ in \mathbb{F}_p^* . We prove similar results for other families of finite groups. In particular, we obtain estimates for the number of cycles for cyclic groups, symmetric groups, dihedral groups and $SL_2(\mathbb{F}_q)$. We also show that the cyclic group of order n minimizes the number of cycles among all nilpotent groups of order n for a fixed exponent a . Finally, we pose several problems.

1. Introduction

Let H be a finite group, and let $a \geq 2$ be an integer. The iterations of the map $x \mapsto x^a$ form a sort of dynamical system in a finite group. As such, it is natural to study the structure of the periodic points of this map. Define the undirected multigraph $G(a, H)$ with vertex set H and $x \sim y$ if $x^a = y$, with an additional edge if $y^a = x$. Note that $G(a, H)$ may have loops (for example at the identity) or cycles of length 2. The orbit structure of the map $x \mapsto x^a$ in G is encoded in $G(a, H)$. This graph has been extensively studied in the case of $H = (\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$ in connection with algorithmic number theory and cryptography (see, e.g., [6], [13] and [17]). In particular, the properties of the well-known Blum-Blum-Shub pseudorandom number generator [4] are determined by the properties of $G(2, (\mathbb{Z}/pq\mathbb{Z})^*)$.

Note that $G(a, H)$ is a refinement of the power graph of H (see [1] and references therein). In particular, the power graph of H is the graph with vertex set H and $x \sim y$ if $x \in \langle y \rangle$ or $y \in \langle x \rangle$. One can build the power graph of H out of $G(a, H)$ by taking the union of the edges of $G(a, H)$ for $1 \leq a \leq |H|$ and deleting any loops or multiple edges.

Let $N(a, H)$ denote the number of connected components in $G(a, H)$. Since each connected component contains a unique cycle, $N(a, H)$ is also the number of cycles in $G(a, H)$. In recent work, Pomerance and Shparlinski gave results on the average order, normal order, and extremal order of $N(a, \mathbb{F}_p^*)$ for p prime.

Figure 1: $G(2, \mathbb{Z}/10\mathbb{Z})$

Theorem 1 ([15, Theorems 1.1 and 1.2]). *For any $a \geq 2$:*

- *There exist infinitely many primes p such that $N(a, \mathbb{F}_p^*) > p^{5/12+o(1)}$.*
- *For almost all primes p , $N(a, \mathbb{F}_p^*) < p^{1/2+o(1)}$.*
- $\frac{1}{\pi(x)} \sum_{p \leq x} N(a, \mathbb{F}_p^*) \gg x^{0.293}$.

Under the assumption of the Elliot-Halberstam conjecture and a strong Linnik’s constant, we can improve this to

$$\frac{1}{\pi(x)} \sum_{p \leq x} N(a, \mathbb{F}_p^*) \geq x^{1+o(1)}.$$

Pomrance and Shparlinski asked for an extension of these results to other groups. We consider the question of the size of $N(a, G)$ for various families of groups. Using results from number theory, group theory, and probability theory, we obtain results on the size of $N(a, G)$ for cyclic groups, dihedral groups, symmetric groups and the special linear group of degree 2 over a finite field.

Next, we conjecture that, for any a , the cyclic groups have the fewest connected components over any groups of a given order. More precisely, we have the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. Let G be a group of order n . Then

$$N(a, G) \geq N(a, C_n).$$

We have verified this conjecture using Sage [16] for all groups of order at most 1000, except for groups of order 768, if $a \in \{2, 3, \dots, 20\}$. We prove the following partial result.

Theorem 2. Let G be a nilpotent group of order n . Then

$$N(a, G) \geq N(a, C_n).$$

In Section 2, we introduce results used to estimate $N(a, G)$. In Section 3, we estimate the normal order, average order, and extremal order of $N(a, G)$ for several families of groups. In Section 4, we prove Theorem 2. In Section 5, we discuss further directions and ask several questions.

1.1. Notation

Throughout this paper, p denotes a prime number, q denotes a prime power, and a denotes a positive integer at least 2. All groups are finite, and group multiplication is always written multiplicatively.

For a set A , we denote the characteristic function of A by $1_A(x)$. For $g \in G$, a group, let $|g|$ denote the order of g . Let $\text{ord}_n(a)$ denote the multiplicative order of a in $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$. For a group G , let $w_G(d)$ denote the number of elements of order d . We will often write $w(d)$ for $w_G(d)$ if the group is obvious. Let C_n denote the cyclic group of order n , D_n denote the dihedral group of order $2n$, $SL_n(\mathbb{F}_q)$ denote the special linear group of degree n over the finite field of q elements and let S_n denote the symmetric group of order $n!$. Let λ denote the Carmichael lambda function, i.e., $\lambda(n)$ is the exponent of $(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z})^*$. Let φ denote the Euler φ -function.

We use standard Vinogradov notation and Landau notation. Recall that the statements $U = O(V)$, $U \ll V$ and $V \gg U$ all mean $|U| \leq cV$ for some $c > 0$. We also use the notation $o(1)$ to denote a quantity that tends to 0 as some parameter goes to infinity. The dependency of the constant on a parameter will be denoted as a subscript. We say almost all elements of a set $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ have a property P if the proportion of the elements of S that have P and are at most n is $1 + o(1)$.

2. General Tools

Our main tool for estimating $N(a, G)$ is the following lemma.

Lemma 1. Let ρ denote the largest factor of $|G|$ relatively prime to a . Then

$$N(a, G) = \sum_{d|\rho} \frac{w(d)}{\text{ord}_d(a)}.$$

Proof. We generalize an argument of Chou and Shparlinski in [6]. Consider the map $x \mapsto x^a$. Let $t \geq 0, c > 0$ be minimal such that $x^{a^t} = x^{a^{t+c}}$ for all x , which exist since the map $x \mapsto x^a$ is preperiodic. Let d denote the order of x . Then $d|a^t(a^c - 1)$, so $t = 0$ if and only if $\gcd(a, d) = 1$. If $t = 0$, then x lies in a cycle of length $\text{ord}_d(a)$, and there are $w(d)$ elements that lie in such cycles, showing the result. \square

We will often use this result in the form

$$N(a, G) = \sum_{\substack{g \in G \\ \gcd(|g|, a) = 1}} \frac{1}{\text{ord}_{|g|}(a)},$$

which follows from Lemma 1 by grouping terms by order. We observe that if a group G has many elements of large order, then $N(a, G)$ is likely to be small. This gives some justification to Conjecture 1. We will also make use of the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *Let $H_1, \dots, H_n \leq G$, and suppose $H_i \cap H_j = \{e\}$ for $i \neq j$, where e is the identity of G . Then*

$$N(a, G) \geq \sum_{i=1}^n N(a, H_i) - n + 1.$$

Proof. Note that the subgraph in $G(a, G)$ induced by H_i is isomorphic to $G(a, H_i)$. These induced subgraphs overlap only at the identity, and, in these induced subgraphs, each connected component contains a unique cycle. In $G(a, G)$, these induced subgraphs cannot be connected to each other, except for the connected component containing the identity. \square

Before proving the last general result, we state a lemma.

Lemma 3. *If $\frac{dd'}{\gcd(d, d')} = n$, then $\text{ord}_d(a) \text{ord}_{d'}(a) \geq \text{ord}_n(a)$.*

Proof. As $d \mid a^{\text{ord}_d(a)} - 1$ and $d' \mid a^{\text{ord}_{d'}(a)} - 1$, $n \mid a^{\text{ord}_d(a) \text{ord}_{d'}(a)} - 1$. \square

Theorem 3. *Let G, H be finite groups. Then*

$$N(a, G \times H) \geq N(a, G)N(a, H).$$

Proof. Let ρ_1 and ρ_2 be the largest divisors coprime to a of $|G|$ and $|H|$ respectively.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{d|\rho_1} \frac{w_G(d)}{\text{ord}_d(a)}\right) \left(\sum_{d'|\rho_2} \frac{w_H(d')}{\text{ord}_{d'}(a)}\right) &= \sum_{d|\rho_1, d'|\rho_2} \frac{w_G(d)w_H(d')}{\text{ord}_d(a) \text{ord}_{d'}(a)} \\ &= \sum_{k|\rho_1\rho_2} \sum_{\substack{d|\rho_1, d'|\rho_2, \\ dd'/\gcd(d, d')=k}} \frac{w_G(d)w_H(d')}{\text{ord}_d(a) \text{ord}_{d'}(a)} \\ &\leq \sum_{k|\rho_1\rho_2} \sum_{\substack{d|\rho_1, d'|\rho_2, \\ dd'/\gcd(d, d')=k}} \frac{w_G(d)w_H(d')}{\text{ord}_k(a)} \\ &= \sum_{k|\rho_1\rho_2} \frac{w_{G \times H}(k)}{\text{ord}_k(a)} \\ &= N(a, G \times H), \end{aligned}$$

where in the inequality we use Lemma 3. □

3. Size of $N(a, G)$

3.1. Cyclic Groups

We show results on the average order, normal order, and extremal order of $N(a, C_n)$.

Theorem 4. *Let $\delta = 0.2961$. Then*

$$\frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} N(a, C_n) \geq x^{1-\delta+o(1)}.$$

Theorem 5. *For any fixed a , there exist infinitely many n such that*

$$N(a, C_n) \geq n^{1+o(1)}.$$

Theorem 6. *For almost all n , we have that*

$$N(a, C_n) \leq n^{1/2+o(1)}.$$

Remark 1. Under the Elliott-Halberstam conjecture, we can remove δ from Theorem 4, i.e., we can show that $\frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} N(a, C_n) \geq x^{1+o(1)}$. Under the generalized Riemann hypothesis, we can remove the $1/2$ from Theorem 6 and show that for almost all n , $N(a, C_n) \leq n^{o(1)}$.

In conjunction with the following lemma, the above theorems immediately give results on dihedral groups.

Lemma 4. *If a is even, then $N(a, D_n) = N(a, C_n)$. If a is odd, then $N(a, D_n) = n + N(a, C_n)$.*

Proof. Recall that D_n consists of a cyclic subgroup of order n and n elements of order 2 lying outside this cyclic subgroup. If a is even, then each element of order 2 is connected to the component that contains the identity. If a is odd, then each element of order 2 lies in a component that consists of a single vertex with a loop. \square

Proof of Theorem 4. We use the strategy of Pomerance and Shparlinski in [15]. First we recall a result of Baker and Harman.

Lemma 5 ([3], Theorem 1). *There is an absolute constant κ with the following property: Let x sufficiently large, and let*

$$v = \frac{\log x}{\log \log x}, \quad w = v^{1/0.2961}.$$

Let

$$\mathcal{Q} = \left\{ p \in \left[\frac{w}{(\log w)^\kappa}, w \right] : p - 1 \mid M_v \right\},$$

where M_v is the least common multiple of the integers in $[1, v]$. Then

$$|\mathcal{Q}| \geq \frac{w}{(\log w)^\kappa}.$$

Now we prove the result. Let \mathcal{Q} be the set of primes given by Lemma 5. Let

$$k = \left\lfloor \frac{\log x}{\log w} \right\rfloor.$$

Let \mathcal{S} denote the set of products of k distinct elements of \mathcal{Q} . We see that

$$|\mathcal{S}| = \binom{|\mathcal{Q}|}{k} = \left(\frac{w}{k} \right)^k x^{o(1)},$$

using that $(n/k)^k \leq \binom{n}{k} \leq (ne/k)^k$. We compute that $k^k = x^{0.2961+o(1)}$ and $w^k = x^{1+o(1)}$, so

$$|\mathcal{S}| = x^{1-0.2961+o(1)}.$$

We also note that, for any $m \in \mathcal{S}$,

$$x \geq w^k \geq m \geq (w/(\log w)^\kappa)^k = x^{1+o(1)}.$$

By Lemma 3, we have that for any $m \in \mathcal{S}$, $\text{ord}_m(a) \mid M_v$. By the prime number theorem, this implies that

$$\text{ord}_m(a) \leq M_v = \exp(v(1 + o(1))) = x^{o(1)}.$$

Therefore, for each $m \in \mathcal{S}$, we have

$$N(a, C_m) \geq \frac{\varphi(m)}{\text{ord}_m(a)} = x^{1+o(1)},$$

since $\varphi(m) = m^{1+o(1)} = x^{1+o(1)}$ [11, Theorem 328]. Therefore we have found $x^{1-0.2961+o(1)}$ positive integers m less than or equal to x such that $N(a, C_m) = x^{1+o(1)}$, which implies the result. \square

Remark 2. One can obtain the same result by using the work of Ambrose; it follows from the specialization to \mathbb{Q} of [2, Theorem 1]. As we can remove δ from the result of Ambrose under the Elliott-Halberstam conjecture, we can show that the average value of $N(a, C_n)$ is $x^{1+o(1)}$ under the Elliott-Halberstam conjecture.

Proof of Theorem 5. Let k be a large integer, and set $n = a^k - 1$. Then, using [11, Theorem 328],

$$N(a, C_n) \geq \frac{\varphi(a^k - 1)}{k} \gg \frac{n}{\log n \log \log n}.$$

\square

Before proving Theorem 6, we recall some properties of the Carmichael lambda function.

Lemma 6 ([9, Lemma 2]). *If $d|n$, then*

$$\varphi(d)/\lambda(d) | \varphi(n)/\lambda(n).$$

Theorem 7 ([8, Theorem 2]). *For almost all n ,*

$$\lambda(n) = n^{1+o(1)}.$$

Lemma 7 ([13, Lemma 5]). *We have*

$$\text{ord}_n(a) \geq \frac{\lambda(n)}{n} \prod_{p|n} \text{ord}_p(a).$$

Let B denote the set of primes p such that $\text{ord}_p(a) < \sqrt{p}/\log p$.

Lemma 8 ([7]). *With B defined as above, $|B \cap \{1, \dots, N\}| = O(N/(\log N)^3)$.*

Remark 3. Using the results in [12], we can show that the set of primes p , with $p \leq n$ and $\text{ord}_p(a) \leq p^{1+o(1)}$, has size $O(n/(\log n)^3)$ under the generalized Riemann hypothesis, which would lead to a corresponding improvement in Theorem 6 to $N(a, C_n) \leq n^{o(1)}$ for almost all n .

For an integer n , let n_B denote the largest divisor of n that is a product of primes from B .

Lemma 9. *For almost all $n \leq N$, $n_B < \log n$.*

Proof. By the density estimate in Lemma 8, we see that

$$\sum_{n=n_B} \frac{1}{n} = \prod_{p \in B} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-1} = O(1).$$

Therefore, for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there is $C = C(\varepsilon)$ such that

$$\sum_{\substack{n=n_B, \\ n > C}} \frac{1}{n} < \varepsilon.$$

Thus for all but εN integers $n \leq N$, we have that $n_B < C$. As ε was arbitrary and eventually $\log n > C$, this proves the claim. \square

Lemma 10 ([13, Lemma 7]). *Let A denote the set of positive integers n such that there is a positive integer s such that $s^2 \mid n$ and $s^2 \geq \log n$. Then $|A \cap \{1, \dots, N\}| = O(N/\log N)$.*

Proof of Theorem 6. By Lemma 7, Lemma 9, and Lemma 10 there is a set S of density 1 such that $n_B < \log n$, $s^2 < \log n$ for every s such that s^2 divides n , and $\lambda(n) = n^{1+o(1)}$ for all $n \in S$. By Lemma 7, we have that

$$N(a, C_n) \leq \sum_{d \mid n} \frac{d\varphi(d)}{\lambda(d) \prod_{p \mid d} \text{ord}_p(a)}.$$

Using the bound that $\varphi(n) < n$ and Lemma 6, in form of $\varphi(d)/\lambda(d) \leq \varphi(n)/\lambda(n)$ for $d \mid n$, we have that, for almost all n ,

$$\begin{aligned} N(a, C_n) &\leq \sum_{d \mid n} \frac{d\varphi(d)}{\lambda(d) \prod_{p \mid d} \text{ord}_p(a)} \\ &\leq \sum_{d \mid n} \frac{d\varphi(n)}{\lambda(n) \prod_{p \mid d} \text{ord}_p(a)} \\ &= \sum_{d \mid n} \frac{dn^{o(1)}}{\prod_{p \mid d} \text{ord}_p(a)} \\ &\leq n^{1/2+o(1)}, \end{aligned}$$

where in the last inequality we are using that the square part of n is at most $\log n$ and the product of the primes in B dividing n is at most $\log n$. \square

3.2. Symmetric Groups

As Lemma 2 implies that the sequence $\{N(a, S_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is non-decreasing, since S_{n-1} embeds into S_n , it makes less sense to discuss the average order, normal order, and extremal order of $N(a, S_n)$. We instead prove bounds on the size of $N(a, S_n)$.

Theorem 8. *We have*

$$N(a, S_n) \geq \frac{n!}{\exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n(1 + o(1))\right)}.$$

Let $T_n = T_n(a)$ denote the set of permutations in S_n with order coprime to a , and let $S(n)$ denote the set of positive integers coprime to a that are at most n . We will use concentration bounds to show that almost all elements of T_n have large order, and then we use the trivial bound that $\text{ord}_d(a) \leq d$ to bound $N(a, S_n)$.

Theorem 9 ([14, Theorem 1]). *There exist constants $C = C(a)$ and $\delta = \delta(a)$ such that*

$$|T_n| = C(n-1)!n^{\varphi(a)/a} + O((n-1)!n^{\varphi(a)/a-\delta}).$$

Lemma 11 ([18, Theorem 1]). *For some permutation σ , let $M(\sigma)$ denote the order of the permutation. Choose a random permutation τ_n from T_n . Then*

$$P\left(\frac{\log M(\tau_n) - \sum_{i \in S(n)} (\log i)/i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i \in S(n)} (\log i)^2/i}} \leq x\right) \xrightarrow{d} \Phi(x),$$

where $\Phi(x)$ is the standard normal distribution and \xrightarrow{d} denotes convergence in distribution.

We use Lemma 11 to bound the order of most elements of T_n and then use the trivial upper bound on $\text{ord}_d(a)$. First we obtain an asymptotic for $\sum_{i \in S(n)} (\log i)^2/i$.

Lemma 12. *We have*

$$\sum_{i \in S(n)} \frac{\log i}{i} = \frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n + o(\log^2 n).$$

Proof. Observe that, using partial summation,

$$\sum_{i \in S(n)} \frac{\log i}{i} = \log n \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1_{S(n)}(i)}{i} + \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} (\log m - \log(m+1)) \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1_{S(n)}(i)}{i}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1_{S(n)}(i)}{i} &= \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{1}{m} - \frac{1}{m+1}\right) m \frac{\varphi(a)}{a} + O(1) \\ &= \frac{\varphi(a)}{a} \log n + O(1). \end{aligned}$$

Using partial summation again, we have that

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\log i}{i} = \log^2 n + \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} (\log m - \log m + 1) \log m + O(\log n).$$

On the other hand,

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\log i}{i} = \int_1^n \frac{\log x}{x} dx + o(\log n) = \frac{\log^2 n}{2} + o(\log n).$$

Hence

$$\sum_{m=1}^{n-1} (\log m - \log m + 1) \log m = \frac{\log^2 n}{2} + o(\log n),$$

showing that

$$\sum_{i \in S(n)} \frac{\log i}{i} = \frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n + o(\log^2 n).$$

□

Proof of Theorem 8. We have the trivial bound

$$\sum_{i \in S(n)} \frac{(\log i)^2}{i} = O(\log^3 n).$$

For all but $o_a(|T_n|)$ permutations τ_n in T_n , we have that

$$\log M(\tau_n) \leq \sum_{i \in S(n)} \frac{\log i}{i} + O(\log \log n (\log n)^{3/2}).$$

Hence, for almost all permutations in T_n , we have that

$$M(\tau_n) \leq \exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n (1 + o(1))\right).$$

In order to turn this into a lower bound for $N(a, S_n)$, we need an upper bound on $\text{ord}_d(a)$ for d coprime to a . Using the trivial bound that $\text{ord}_d(a) \leq d \leq \exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n (1 + o(1))\right)$ for almost all permutations $\tau_n \in T_n$, we have that

$$N(a, S_n) \gg_a \frac{(n-1)! n^{\varphi(a)/a}}{\exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n (1 + o(1))\right)} = \frac{n!}{\exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n (1 + o(1))\right)}.$$

□

We conjecture that this lower bound is of the correct order, as the trivial bound $\text{ord}_d(a) \leq d$ is usually fairly sharp for most d . Without finer control over the orders of permutations than is known, it seems difficult to prove a sharp upper bound. However, we can show that

$$N(a, S_n) = o_a((n - 1)!n^{\varphi(a)/a}).$$

Indeed, by Lemma 11, we have that for all but $o_a(|T_n|)$ elements of T_n ,

$$M(\tau_n) \geq \exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n(1 + o(1))\right).$$

Hence

$$N(a, S_n) \leq o_a(|T_n|) + \frac{(n - 1)!n^{\varphi(a)/a}}{\exp\left(\frac{\varphi(a)}{2a} \log^2 n(1 + o(1))\right)} = o_a((n - 1)!n^{\varphi(a)/a}).$$

3.3. Special Linear Groups Over Finite Fields

Because of highly explicit knowledge of the conjugacy class structure of $SL_2(\mathbb{F}_q)$, we are able to compute $N(a, SL_2(\mathbb{F}_q))$.

Theorem 10. *Let $q = p^c$ be an odd prime power. If $\gcd(a, q) = 1$, then*

$$N(a, SL_2(\mathbb{F}_q)) = \frac{q^2 - q}{2}N(a, C_{q+1}) + \frac{q^2 + q}{2}N(a, C_{q-1}) + (q^2 - 1)(1 + 1_{2 \nmid a})\left(\frac{1}{\text{ord}_p(a)} - 1\right),$$

where $1_{2 \nmid a}$ is 1 if a is odd and 0 otherwise. If $\gcd(a, q) > 1$, then the last term does not appear.

Before we begin the proof, we recall some facts about conjugacy classes in $SL_2(\mathbb{F}_q)$ for q odd. We break the conjugacy classes into 4 types (see, e.g., [10]).

- Type 1: The $(q - 3)/2$ conjugacy classes of elements which are diagonalizable of \mathbb{F}_q ; they are parametrized by matrices of the form $\begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha^{-1} \end{pmatrix}$ for $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_q^* \setminus \{1, -1\}$. Each conjugacy class has $q(q + 1)$ elements.
- Type 2: The $(q - 1)/2$ conjugacy classes of elements which are diagonalizable of \mathbb{F}_{q^2} but not \mathbb{F}_q ; they are parametrized by matrices of the form $\begin{pmatrix} \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & \alpha^{-1} \end{pmatrix}$ for $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_{q^2}^* \setminus \{1, -1\}$ and satisfying $\alpha \cdot Fr(\alpha) = \alpha^{q+1} = 1$, where Fr denotes the Frobenius endomorphism. Each conjugacy class has $q(q - 1)$ elements.
- Type 3: The central conjugacy classes $\{I\}$ and $\{-I\}$.

- Type 4: The 4 conjugacy classes that are not semi-simple. These conjugacy classes are parametrized by $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} -1 & b \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$, where b is a non-square in \mathbb{F}_q . There are $(q^2 - 1)/2$ elements in each conjugacy class.

Proof. Note that the order of an element in a type 1 conjugacy classes is just the order of the eigenvalue, and the eigenvalues lie in the cyclic group \mathbb{F}_q^* . Therefore, because each type 1 conjugacy class has eigenvalues α and α^{-1} , there are $\varphi(d)/2$ type 1 conjugacy classes of order d for each divisor d of $q - 1$, $d \neq 1, 2$. Hence

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C} \text{ type 1}} \frac{1}{\text{ord}_d(a)} = \frac{q^2 + q}{2} (N(a, C_{q-1}) - 1 - 1_{2 \nmid a}).$$

Similarly for type 2, we note that the elements of \mathbb{F}_{q^2} satisfying $x^{q+1} = 1$ form a cyclic subgroup of the multiplicative group. Therefore

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C} \text{ type 2}} \frac{1}{\text{ord}_d(a)} = \frac{q^2 - q}{2} (N(a, C_{q-1}) - 1 - 1_{2 \nmid a}).$$

For type 3, the contribution is $1 + 1_{2 \nmid a}$.

For type 4, each element with eigenvalue 1 has order p , and each element with eigenvalue -1 has order $2p$. Hence,

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{C} \text{ type 4}} \frac{1}{\text{ord}_d(a)} = \frac{q^2 - 1}{\text{ord}_p(a)} + 1_{2 \nmid a} \frac{q^2 - 1}{\text{ord}_{2p}(a)} = \frac{q^2 - 1}{\text{ord}_p(a)} (1 + 1_{2 \nmid a}),$$

since $\text{ord}_{2p}(a) = \text{ord}_p(a)$ for a odd. Summing over the 4 types of conjugacy classes gives the result. \square

Theorem 1 allows us to bound the normal and extremal order of $N(a, SL_2(\mathbb{F}_p))$, using the fact that $N(a, SL_2(\mathbb{F}_p)) \gg p^2 N(a, \mathbb{F}_p^*)$.

Corollary 1. *There exist infinitely many primes p such that*

$$N(a, SL_2(\mathbb{F}_p)) \geq p^{29/12 + o(1)}.$$

We also have

$$\frac{1}{\pi(x)} \sum_{p \leq x} N(a, SL_2(\mathbb{F}_p)) \gg x^{2.293}.$$

4. On the Minimal Size of $N(a, G)$ Among Groups of a Fixed Order

We now prove Theorem 2. Our strategy is to show that, for a group G of order n , the sum $\sum_{g \in G, \text{gcd}(|g|, a) = 1} \frac{1}{\text{ord}_{|g|}(a)}$ majorizes $\sum_{g \in C_n, \text{gcd}(|g|, a) = 1} \frac{1}{\text{ord}_{|g|}(a)}$ for any

nilpotent group G . Then, Lemma 1 immediately implies Theorem 2. Before proving Theorem 2, we prove a lemma. For a group G , let $B_G(n)$ denote the number of elements of order at least n in G .

Lemma 13. *Let G be a group of order p^k . Then for all n , $B_G(n) \leq B_{C_{p^k}}(n)$.*

Proof. First observe that the number of elements of order n in any finite group is a multiple of $\varphi(n)$. Suppose G is a counterexample to the lemma, then choose ℓ such that $B_G(p^\ell) > B_{C_{p^k}}(p^\ell)$. Since $B_G(1) = B_{C_{p^k}}(1)$, there must be fewer than $\varphi(p^b)$ elements of order p^b for some $b < \ell$. Hence there are no elements of order p^b for some b . But if a group has an element of order p^c , then it also has an element of order p^b for every $b < c$. \square

Proof of Theorem 2. We first prove Theorem 2 for p -groups. Note that $\text{ord}_{p^b}(a) \leq \text{ord}_{p^c}(a)$ if $b \leq c$. But then Lemma 13 and Lemma 1 immediately imply that $N(a, G) \geq N(a, C_{|G|})$ for any p -group G .

Recall that a group is nilpotent if and only if it is a direct product of p -groups. Let $G = P_1 \times \dots \times P_k$ be a nilpotent group, and let P_1, \dots, P_k be p -groups with orders $p_i^{e_i}$ for distinct primes p_1, \dots, p_k . Let $n = |G|$. We may assume that $\text{gcd}(a, n) = 1$, as factors of p -group with g not relatively prime a do not affect the result. We need to show that

$$\sum_{d|n} \frac{w(d)}{\text{ord}_d(a)} \geq \sum_{d|n} \frac{\varphi(d)}{\text{ord}_d(a)}.$$

Observe that, for a nilpotent group G , w_G is a multiplicative function, i.e.,

$$w_G(p_1^{j_1} p_2^{j_2} \dots p_k^{j_k}) = w_G(p_1^{j_1}) w_G(p_2^{j_2}) \dots w_G(p_k^{j_k}).$$

We claim that for any set of ℓ primes, $p_{i_1}, \dots, p_{i_\ell}$, we have that

$$\sum_{d=p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_\ell}^{b_\ell}} \frac{w(d)}{\text{ord}_d(a)} \geq \sum_{d=p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_\ell}^{b_\ell}} \frac{\varphi(d)}{\text{ord}_d(a)}.$$

This would clearly imply the result by summing over all subsets of the primes dividing n . We prove the claim by induction on ℓ . The base case is the case of p -groups. Fix $b_1, \dots, b_{\ell-1}$ such that $p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}} \mid n$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{j_{i_\ell}} \frac{w(p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}} p_{i_\ell}^k)}{\text{ord}_{p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}} p_{i_\ell}^k}(a)} &= w(p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}}) \sum_{k=0}^{j_{i_\ell}} \frac{w(p_{i_\ell}^k)}{\text{ord}_{p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}} p_{i_\ell}^k}(a)} \\ &\geq \frac{w(p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}})}{\text{ord}_{p_{i_1}^{b_1} \dots p_{i_{\ell-1}}^{b_{\ell-1}}}(a)} \sum_{k=0}^{j_{i_\ell}} \frac{w(p_{i_\ell}^k)}{\text{ord}_{p_{i_\ell}^k}(a)}, \end{aligned}$$

where we use Lemma 3 in the inequality. The result follows from summing over all choices of $b_1, \dots, b_{\ell-1}$ and the inductive hypothesis. \square

5. Discussion

In addition to proving a better upper bound on $N(a, S_n)$ and proving Conjecture 1, we pose several open problems.

Since the map $x \mapsto x^a$ is eventually periodic, the orbit x, x^a, x^{a^2}, \dots consists of a tail which does not repeat followed by a cycle. If x has no tail, then we say that x is *purely periodic*. Thus in $G(a, H)$, every purely periodic element has a rooted tree of tails leading into it. In [6, Theorem 1], Chou and Shparlinski showed that if H is cyclic, then all of the tails coming off the purely periodic elements in H are isomorphic. In particular, every purely periodic element has tails of the same size. This enabled Chou and Shparlinski to give a simple expression for the average length of the period over all elements of C_n . Let $C(a, G)$ denote the average period of an element in G . Then

Theorem 11 ([6, Theorem 1]). *If ρ is the largest divisor of n coprime to a , then*

$$C(a, C_n) = \frac{1}{\rho} \sum_{d|\rho} \varphi(d) \text{ord}_d(a).$$

For general groups, the tails coming off a purely periodic vertex are not the same size. It would be interesting to compute or bound $C(a, G)$ for various families of groups.

By analogy with the power graph, it would be interesting to determine what set of invariants is determined by $G(a, H)$ for some fixed a or for all a . Groups H of prime exponent and the same order clearly have the same $G(a, H)$ for every a . Using the example of Cameron and Ghosh in [5], we see that, if $H = \langle x, y \mid x^3 = y^3 = [x, y]^3 = 1 \rangle$, the smallest non-abelian group of exponent 3, then $G(a, C_3 \times C_3 \times C_3) \cong G(a, H)$ for every a . This raises the following question.

Question 1. Are there groups H and K such that the power graph of H is isomorphic to the power graph of K , but $G(a, H)$ is not isomorphic to $G(a, K)$ for some a ?

It would be interesting to compute the asymptotics of $N(a, SL_n(\mathbb{F}_q))$ as n grows, in analogy with the symmetric group. As in the case of $N(a, S_n)$, Lemma 2 implies that the sequence $\{N(a, SL_n(\mathbb{F}_q))\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is non-decreasing since $SL_{n-1}(\mathbb{F}_q)$ embeds into $SL_n(\mathbb{F}_q)$.

One could also allow a to vary. Let $\text{exp}(G)$ denote the exponent of G . Then clearly $N(a, G) = N(a + \text{exp}(G), G)$. Then the following question is natural.

Question 2. What $a \in \{2, 3, \dots, \text{exp}(G) - 1\}$ maximizes $N(a, S_n)$?

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